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Ratsa Veronika Volodymyrivna –
Assistant, Department of Internal Medicine,
Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine
Abdullaeva Nurlana Imrankyzy –
4th-year student of the 6th group
at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine
Berezka Evelina Ihorivna –
4th-year student of the 6th group
at the BSMU in Chernivtsi, Ukraine
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THE IMPORTANCE OF SE AND SELENOPROTEIN P IN THE FUNCTIONING OF THE THYROID AND PANCREAS

Abstract

The study of micro- and macroelements is very relevant in the conditions of modern science. All over the world there is a wide demand for taking these drugs, but the impact on the human body is not fully known. We are interested in the influence of selenium (Se) on endocrine glands, in particular the thyroid and pancreas, and in biochemical processes for the prevention and treatment of endocrinological diseases.

Key words: selenium, selenoprotein P, thyroid gland, pancreas

Today, it is believed that a number of elements, including iodine, selenium, iron, zinc, copper and calcium, are necessary for the normal functioning of the endocrine glands. Selenium (Se) takes the leading place among these trace elements.[1] Over the last decades, the understanding of the importance of Se for human health has increased significantly. In 1817, the Swedish chemist Jons Jacob Berzelius discovered this non-metallic element and named it Se. For 150 years after its discovery, selenium was considered toxic.[2]

An atom of Se (80Se) has 34 protons and 46 neutrons. It is an element of group 16 (VIa), period 4, in which the outer 4p-orbit is filled with 4 electrons ([Ar]3d104s24p4). There are six naturally occurring isotopes with neutron numbers: 74Se (0.87%), 76Se (9.02%), 77Se (7.58%), 78Se (23.52%), 80Se (49.82%) and 82Se (9.19%). Selenium is an intermediate link between metals and non-metals. It has redox states: 2– (selenide, Se^{2–}), 0 (elemental Se), 4+ (selenite, SeO₃^{2–}) and 6+ (selenate, SeO₄^{2–}).[3]

Selenium is an important component of many enzymes. It is well known for its role as an antioxidant and in immune processes, where it can be incorporated into body proteins instead of the amino acid methionine. According to research, Se has many functions in the human body, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-mutagenic, anti-carcinogenic, antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal effects. [4,5,6]

Selenium deficiency is quite common among the population and can be significant in patients with various pathologies due to genetic or environmental causes, as well as due to the intake of certain medications. Se is used for the prevention and treatment of various diseases such as cardiovascular disease, hypothyroidism, stroke, atherosclerosis, cancer, HIV, pancreatitis, depression and diabetes. [7]

Recent studies show that organoselenium compounds can cause ferroptosis of cancer cells.

Selenium has unique biochemical properties and plays an important role in the regulation of ferroptosis. Dibenzylselenide is a powerful prooxidant and a unique inducer of ferroptosis both in vitro and in vivo.[8,9]

Studies also indicate the existence of a U-shaped curve between selenium levels and body health. [10,11] Patients with selenium deficiency may benefit from selenium supplementation, while selenium excess may increase the risk of certain diseases. The form of selenium in food affects its absorption by the body. Organic forms of selenium have higher bioavailability than inorganic forms, and selenium from plant foods is better absorbed than from animal foods.

Thus, selenium deficiency can cause various disorders. For example, in patients with chronic pancreatitis, selenium deficiency is often observed due to insufficient digestive enzymes and the body's inability to adequately absorb nutrients. An insufficient level of selenium can be one of the predictors of the development and progress of chronic pancreatitis.[12,13,14,15,16]

Modern research emphasizes the importance of three trace elements - iodine, selenium and iron - in the biosynthesis and activation of thyroid hormones. Deficiency of these trace elements and impaired sensitivity to thyroid hormones can lead to various disorders. A meta-analysis of genetic data has shown that individuals with a high genetic risk are significantly more likely to suffer from hypothyroidism.[17,18,19]

Selenoprotein P in humans is a monomeric glycoprotein containing 10 selenocysteine (Sec) residues, making it unique among other selenoproteins. Sec is the only natural amino acid that does not have its own aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase, so its biosynthesis requires a specific pathway. First, seryl-tRNA synthetase (SerRS) binds selenocysteine-specific

tRNA (Sec tRNA) to Ser to form Seryl-tRNA Sec, which is then converted to Sec-tRNA Sec by O-phosphoseryl-tRNA Sec kinase and selenocysteine synthase. Sec-tRNA Sec can interact with protein 2, which recognizes the UGA stop codon. The decoding of the UGA codon as Sec requires a Sec insertion element (SECIS) in the 3'-untranslated region of the mRNA. During the interaction of SECIS and SBP2, Sec is transported to the ribosome and inserted into the nascent polypeptide chain, enabling the synthesis of selenoprotein P.[20,21,22]

Selenoprotein P, after synthesis, enters the blood and transports Se to other tissues and organs. It accounts for approximately half of the total concentration of Se in human blood plasma and is able to bind to specific receptors on cell membranes to deliver Se into cells.

Studies show that selenoprotein P is important for maintaining Se levels in the brain. It carries 10 selenocysteine residues: one in the N-terminal domain with redox activity and nine in the C-terminal domain, which deliver Se to the brain via low-density lipoprotein-associated receptor protein 8 at the blood-brain barrier. [23]

Elevated selenoprotein P is associated with type 2 diabetes because it can impair pancreatic β -cell function and suppress insulin secretion. However, randomized clinical trials have not confirmed a significant adverse effect of daily Se supplementation on β -cell function or insulin sensitivity.[24,25,26]

Intake of Se through food, drugs, or dietary supplements is a key factor affecting Se levels in the body, but gender, age, menopause, body mass index, cigarette smoking, presence of comorbidities, and genotype are also important.

Studying the effect of Se on the human body is a very promising scientific direction, because in the future it will prevent the occurrence of various nosologies.

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